

Energy and Carbon Footprint Reduction for Hybrid Heat-Integrated Distillation Systems: Robust Model Predictive Control Approach

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Abstract

Industrial distillation processes consume a significant amount of energy, making control improvements essential to reduce operating costs and minimise environmental impact. This paper presents a robust model predictive control strategy for hybrid heat-integrated distillation systems, focusing on the effects of progressive fouling in key process components. The control approach is based on an offset-free implicit tube formulation that accounts for uncertainties arising from fouling on heat-transfer surfaces. A dynamic simulation model is developed to evaluate the proposed control strategy in comparison with conventional proportional-integral-derivative controllers. Two widely used control tasks are considered: setpoint tracking and disturbance rejection. Each task is analysed under four fouling levels corresponding to realistic industrial operating conditions. Results demonstrate that the robust predictive controller improves closed-loop performance, reducing the control error by over 35% and eliminating overshoot under conservative tuning. More aggressive tuning results in faster responses with minimal oscillations. The proposed control method also reduces energy demands, fuel oil consumption, and associated carbon emissions compared to conventional control. This study demonstrates that the proposed robust model predictive control strategy offers an effective solution for maintaining stable and efficient operation in distillation systems, particularly in the presence of fouling.

Keywords

HIDiC system; Heat and mass exchanger; Closed-loop process analysis; Dynamic model; Robust model predictive control; Control quality indices

1. Introduction

Distillation columns are widely used in global industry, accounting for approximately 95% of separation processes and consuming about 3% of the world's total energy. In contrast, Heat-Integrated Distillation Column (HIDiC) technology can achieve 40–60% lower heat consumption compared to conventional systems [1]. This suggests that implementing HIDiC technology could potentially reduce global energy consumption and associated greenhouse gas emissions by up to 1.5%.

The distillation column and associated machinery, such as the condenser and reboiler, provide the foundation of conventional industrial technology (Figure 1a). This type of thermal separation system is characterised by significant heat loss in the condenser (\dot{Q}_C) and high energy

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demand in the reboiler (\dot{Q}_R). Improving the energy efficiency of distillation units, which are often the most energy-intensive components of processing plants, is crucial in keeping with the worldwide push for sustainable development. For potential future uses and advancements, many authors of research papers are investigating many distillation processes [2]. Despite decades of development, HIDiC technology has not yet been commercialised [3], primarily due to high investment costs, complicated equipment designs, control issues resulting from strong interaction, and nonlinearity [4]. Divided-Wall Columns (DWCs) [5], Petyluk columns, multi-effect columns, heat-pump aided columns [6], diabatic distillation columns, inter-coupled columns, concentric columns [7], and most importantly, HIDiCs [3] are some examples of innovations as well. HIDiCs are one of the methods that have been extensively researched in the literature to reduce energy usage. A compressor is often used with a HIDiC to increase the pressure in the rectifying section (R1) compared to the stripping section (S1) – see Figure 1b. Heat recovery \dot{Q} is made possible from the rectifying to the stripping section through the wall. Because HIDiC designs work well for challenging separations such as close-boiling mixtures, they have gained significant recognition among contemporary intensified distillation columns [8]. Conventional columns typically result in high energy consumption and operational costs when used for such challenging separations. These benefits result from the fact that, unlike traditional columns, which receive the whole energy supply in the reboiler and release it through the condenser, heat transfer in HIDiC columns is spread across the columns' stages [9].

Figure 1. Process flow diagram of a classic industrial rectification column - (a) and HIDiC - (b).

In the study [10], the authors created a simulator for dynamic distillation and illustrated the dynamics of the HIDiC. The rectifying section's changeable column pressure on each tray, as well as the dynamics of vapour hold-up and energy balance, are all taken into account by the simulator. The authors also investigated the impact of pressure on the purity of the products. The delay-time effect during a step change in pressure on the transient state of the system was investigated using an appropriate equation, with a duration of influence expected to be a few seconds. As HIDiCs have been shown to exhibit dynamic behaviour similar to conventional distillation columns, no significant technical barriers are expected for their implementation in industrial control systems. To reduce the system's energy consumption, Huang et al. [11] investigated the dynamics of the HIDiC and its modification and control settings [12]. The authors of the paper [13] employed the mass and energy balance equations, assuming

thermodynamic equilibrium between the liquid and vapour phases, to construct the dynamic model of the HIDiC. A significant degree of nonlinearity was observed in the study between the transient input and output signals, for example, a rise in the gain parameter under various operational scenarios. Several control setups of the enhanced HIDiC were provided by Nakaiwa et al. [14]. The authors assert that residue liquid reflux and distillate reflux are the most effective parameters for regulating the HIDiC among the feedback control variations they present in the paper.

Research in equipment design and optimisation, as well as suitable control systems and their characteristics, is the main emphasis of recent publications on steady-state and dynamic models for HIDiC variations. Regarding the process-equipment coupling, Seo et al. [15] demonstrated that, assuming the same product purity and reaction extent, the internal HIDiC has an advantage over other direct sequences and the Reactive Dividing Wall Column (RDWC) because it can achieve lower internal flow rates and energy consumption. According to the author, applying the HIDiC with a partial double annular structure reduces energy use by 15.4% compared to the direct sequence and 14.4% compared to the RDWC.

Velázquez et al. [16] proposed a two-step hybrid optimisation approach to optimise HIDiCs with heat integration opportunities. This approach starts with deterministic optimisation (solving a Mixed-Integer Nonlinear Programming – MILP problem) to determine the best heat-integrated locations. The second step involves stochastic optimisation (simulated annealing) to verify the optimality of the first step's result and confirm the optimal heat integration, ensuring the lowest energy expenditure.

Gutiérrez-Guerra and Segovia-Hernández [17] published a study outlining a novel approach to building and improving HIDiCs using Aspen Plus and a stochastic optimisation algorithm. This approach was developed to better search for optimal solutions while addressing convergence concerns and preserving a continuous optimisation process. The optimisation of the HIDiCs during the separation of four close-boiling binary mixtures demonstrated the efficacy of the procedure. The findings showed that addressing the design and optimisation of these columns worked well.

The advantages of the HIDiC concept are also studied in the context of batch distillation. For instance, Jana [18] proposed a HIDiC setup for batch processing, which demonstrates a notable reduction in energy usage, cost, and CO₂ emissions. The author proposed a heat-pump-assisted Vapour Recompression (VRC) mechanism to operate the hybrid batch HIDiC-VRC system under transient conditions.

Coming to control issues, the authors of the article [19] investigated the temperature Proportional-Integral-Derivative (PID) control loop-based dynamic performance of simplified DWCs. The results indicated that simplified DWC systems can achieve adequate dynamic performance even without the inclusion of vapour splits as manipulated variables.

A study by Gutiérrez-Guerra et al. [20] demonstrated HIDiCs' dynamic performance. The best HIDiC designs that had previously undergone optimisation were assessed for dynamic performance using a restricted Boltzmann-based distribution estimation approach. Eight close-boiling mixtures with different relative volatile concentrations were used as case studies. Process analysis was used to get the dynamic behaviour in both closed and open loops. The results showed that the HIDiCs perform less dynamically than their conventional equivalents in every case study.

Most recently, Gutiérrez-Guerra and Segovia-Hernández [21] studied the influence of control features on the economical and energy-efficient operation of HIDiCs with different feed compositions. The control characteristics were determined through closed-loop process analysis of the HIDiCs using PI controllers and the Integral Absolute Error (IAE) criterion, along with extensive simulations in Aspen Dynamics. The results show that the HIDiC configurations with the best dynamic behaviour are not compatible with the HIDiC columns

with the best energy and economic performance. However, poor HIDiC setups provided marginally fewer energy and economic advantages but better dynamic features when compared to the best HIDiC configurations.

Figure 2. Process flow diagram of HHIDiS for separating binary (A+B) mixtures.

The present authors' contributions to the research on control systems for HIDiC-type distillation began with a study by Markowski et al. [1] on the mathematical modelling of the Hybrid Heat-Integrated Distillation System (HHIDiS), as shown in Figure 2. Sections R1 and S2 of the distillation system serve as heat integration sections, while sections S1 and R2 serve as process stabilisation in the dynamic state. In this case, HIDiC is built as a channel-type or plate Heat and Mass Exchanger (HME), with the R1 and S2 components designed as plate exchangers, thermally connected to the conventional columns' S1 stripping and R2 rectifying sections. The S1 and R2 sections serve as accumulators for both heat and mass, which contributes to stabilising the R1 and R2 sections during dynamic operation. A typical HIDiC system (Figure 1b) is robust against disturbances and can be controlled effectively by a PID process control system. Therefore, the controllability of the HHIDiS is a central theme of the present study. However, the HME in HHIDiS (R1+S2 section – Figure 2) is not a significant accumulator of heat and mass as a separate entity. Thus, it may be challenging to control such a system using a PID controller because it can become unstable in a dynamic state due to a two-phase flow.

The primary objective of this type of system is twofold: to lower heat consumption through the integration of R1 and S2 and to enhance the dynamic stability of the HHIDiS. In contrast to previous methods where the compressor adjusts the pressure difference (see Figure 1b), this technology, unlike other technologies reported in the literature, adjusts the pressure difference between the R1 and S2 sections using a pump and a valve, as shown in Figure 2. The authors' suggested method may require a lower investment cost and be less vulnerable to technological malfunctions. The proposed configuration is expected to reduce energy consumption by approximately 10%.

The investigation of control qualities using a unique model of HME in a transient state, applied in the HHIDiS, was conducted in recent work [22]. The outcomes demonstrated the dynamic

stability of the channel-type exchanger subject to industrial constraints. Furthermore, the authors discovered that the distillate purity is not highly susceptible to limitations associated with the fouling on the heat transfer surface or the hold-up of liquid inside the channel of the HME exchanger. According to the authors, the distillate purity is decreased by 1%. The study demonstrated that, with the suggested technology, the standard PID controller offers a viable option for handling industrial constraints.

However, as the PID control approach has its limitations, industrial distillation systems can benefit from applying Model Predictive Control (MPC), which belongs to the class of advanced control strategies. According to [23], the MPC for HIDIcs has demonstrated superior control performance over decentralised systems in reducing IAE for top and bottom composition control. MPC is nowadays used in various industrial applications because it can optimise control performance and energy consumption. Recent work on energy supply to buildings [24] demonstrated the effectiveness of MPC with a setpoint optimiser in reducing energy consumption in underfloor heating systems, achieving annual energy savings of 300 kWh more compared to MPC with a constant temperature setpoint.

Moreover, robust MPC, which combines robust control principles with the optimal control strategy of MPC, is particularly promising, offering the option to handle different types of uncertainties. In [25], robust MPC was used to control the shell-and-tube heat exchanger, with the heat exchange operation influenced by fouling and the device's time-variant parameters. The results of the simulation case study confirmed a significant improvement in control performance and energy savings compared to PI control. Recent studies [26] have introduced data-driven approaches to model uncertainty in composition predictions using historical data. By integrating principal component analysis and kernel density estimation, data-driven uncertainty sets can be constructed, allowing for the development of robust MPC algorithms. These methods have demonstrated the ability to maintain product quality while reducing quality surplus and operating costs in composition control for distillation columns.

1.1. Novelty of the work

In the present paper, a robust MPC approach is proposed, specifically an offset-free implicit tube model-based predictive control, for a HHIDS equipped with a plate-type HME (Figure 2). Although existing literature addresses the energy-saving potential of compressor-based HIDIc systems, these studies often neglect the effects of gradual fouling in critical components, thereby limiting their practical relevance. Additionally, previously proposed PID-based control strategies have not been sufficiently robust to handle these time-varying disturbances effectively. In contrast to earlier studies that relied on compressor-based integration, the presented system configuration eliminates the compressor, thereby reducing complexity and associated costs, and introduces a novel heat integration mechanism between two separate distillation columns. Additionally, the developed control methodology explicitly accounts for realistic industrial constraints, including the gradual build-up of fouling phenomena that occur in critical components such as the condenser, reboiler, and integrated exchanger.

The control strategies proposed here are systematically evaluated through a comprehensive simulation-based framework under varying operational conditions and disturbance scenarios, including multiple levels of fouling severity. This study aims to explore the potential advantages of a robust MPC framework in maintaining stable and efficient system operation despite disturbances, ultimately highlighting its relevance for practical, real-world distillation systems where sustainability, reliability, and economic performance are critical factors.

To the best of our knowledge, this is the first work to combine dynamic fouling modelling with robust MPC in a compressor-free HHIDIS setup, offering a new perspective on control system design under realistic, disturbance-prone operating conditions. Compared to previously published robust MPC frameworks, the implicit-tube formulation presented here significantly

reduces computational complexity, making it highly suitable for practical implementation in industrial-scale operations. This research not only enhances understanding of dynamic control in heat-integrated systems but also provides a scalable and energy-efficient alternative to PID-based solutions.

The practical implementation of the proposed robust MPC strategy depends heavily on the availability of accurate dynamic models, as precise model predictions are essential for effective predictive control. Since the analysis conducted in this study is based on simulation, further validation through experimental and industrial testing would enhance the generalisation and adaptability of the results to various distillation setups and mixtures. Nevertheless, the implicit-tube-based MPC framework, which does not rely on computationally demanding set-based operations, shows promising potential for deployment in large-scale industrial processes, efficiently addressing disturbances and supporting stable and reliable operations from a managerial standpoint.

2. Methods

The *Methods* section outlines the theoretical and computational approaches employed to achieve the research objectives. It begins with the formulation of a dynamic model of the HHIDiS, explicitly incorporating realistic operational conditions such as fouling. Subsequent subsections describe the mathematical modelling of individual system components and introduce the robust offset-free implicit tube MPC strategy applied in this study. This structured approach enables a rigorous comparison with conventional PID controllers (Figure 3), particularly under varying levels of fouling and operational disturbances, and supports a comprehensive analysis of control performance, energy efficiency, and environmental impact.

Figure 3. Process control system for the HHIDiS (symbols according to Figure 2).

2.1. Dynamic model of a hybrid heat-integrated distillation system

The mathematical model of the apparatus was adopted from the paper by Markowski et al. [1]. The abbreviation HME refers to the plate-type (or channel-type) heat and mass exchanger developed by the authors, which enables simultaneous diaphragm-based heat exchange and

distillation operations. This configuration was selected due to its lower capital cost compared to conventional designs, such as shell-and-tube heat exchangers [27]. Figure 4a illustrates the concept of thermal coupling of R1 and S2 sections, which is widely recognised in the literature.

Figure 4. The concept involves reconfiguring the rectifying section R1 of column C1 and the stripping section S2 of column C2 into a plate HME. This includes: a) the idea of heat integration between R1 and S2, b) column profiles T–H, and c) an HME constructed from channels using a Z-type plate exchanger [27].

The mathematical model for the HME system integrates two distinct approaches: the Diaphragm Heat Exchange Model (formulated using principles from thermal resistance theory) and the Mass Transfer Model (grounded in the theoretical tray concept commonly applied to distillation processes).

The diaphragm heat exchange process is quantified using standard equations that are widely employed in heat exchanger calculations and referenced in [1]:

$$d\dot{Q} = U_f \cdot \Delta T \cdot dA \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{1}{U_f} = \frac{1}{h_b} + \frac{1}{h_c} + R_f \quad (2)$$

where:

- boiling heat transfer coefficient

$$h_b = h_L \left[\left(\frac{Pr_L + 1}{2} \right) (\varphi_L^2) \right]^{2(\rho_V/\rho_L)^{0.25}} \quad (3)$$

- condensation heat transfer coefficient

$$h_c = a \cdot \lambda_L \left[\frac{\rho_L(\rho_L - \rho_V)g}{\eta_L^2} \right]^b Re_L^c Pr_L^d \quad (4)$$

where the turbulent flow coefficients [1] are $a=0.02$, $b=0.33$, $c=0.35$, $d=0.33$.

Equation (1) determines the temperature difference, ΔT , by analysing the column profiles of the rectifying section (R1) and the stripping section (S2). The heat integration mechanism between these two sections, a concept widely discussed in the literature, along with their respective T-H column profiles, is illustrated in Figure 4ab.

Commonly used equations in the calculations of the distillation column describe the mass transfer phenomena, employing the concept of the theoretical tray [1].

A set of cells addressed using the lumped-parameter technique comprised the channel-type exchanger model (Figure 4c). Differential equations from the mass and energy balances were used to characterise each cell. Additionally, each cell was placed in an area with intensive vapour-liquid mixing. Subsequently, the theoretical tray was assumed to correspond to the mixing zone.

The balances for the j -th mixing region, representing an equivalent theoretical tray (refer to Figure 5), are as follows:

- Energy balance:

$$\dot{N}_{j-1}^L \cdot h_{j-1}^L + \dot{N}_{j+1}^V \cdot h_{j+1}^V + \Delta\dot{Q}_{mj} - \dot{N}_j^V \cdot h_j^V - \dot{N}_j^L \cdot h_j^L = 0 \quad (5)$$

- Mass balance:

$$\dot{N}_{j-1}^L + \dot{N}_{j+1}^V - \dot{N}_j^V - \dot{N}_j^L = 0 \quad (6)$$

The mass balance for component A in the j -th mixing region is as follows:

$$\dot{N}_{j-1}^L \cdot x_{A,j-1} + \dot{N}_{j+1}^V \cdot y_{A,j+1} - \dot{N}_j^V \cdot y_{A,j} - \dot{N}_j^L \cdot x_{A,j} = 0 \quad (7)$$

Thermodynamic equilibrium is maintained between the vapour and liquid phases:

$$T_j^L = T_j^V \quad (8)$$

$$y_A = k_A \cdot x_A \quad (9)$$

Under steady-state conditions, the following relationships are satisfied:

$$\Delta\dot{Q}_{im} = \Delta\dot{Q}_{mj} \quad (10)$$

Similarly, the mass and energy balances for the i -th cell, as shown in Figure 5, are derived using the same methodology applied to the j -th cell, described in Eqs. (5)-(10).

Figure 5. Diagram of Z-type plates division on cells „i” and „j” used for mass and energy balances.

Equation (5), originally formulated for steady-state conditions, can describe a dynamic state by accounting for heat accumulation in cell “j” [22]. Specifically:

$$\frac{d(N_j \cdot h_j^L)}{dt} = \dot{N}_{j-1}^L \cdot h_{j-1}^L + \dot{N}_{j+1}^V \cdot h_{j+1}^V + \Delta\dot{Q}_{mj} - \dot{N}_j^V \cdot h_j^V - \dot{N}_j^L \cdot h_j^L \quad (11)$$

The energy balance for the i -th mixing region, analogous to the steady-state case (see Figure 5), is given as:

$$\frac{d(N_i \cdot h_i^L)}{dt} = \dot{N}_{i-1}^L \cdot h_{i-1}^L + \dot{N}_{i+1}^V \cdot h_{i+1}^V - \dot{N}_i^L \cdot h_i^L - \dot{N}_i^V \cdot h_i^V - \Delta\dot{Q}_{im} \quad (12)$$

The energy balance for the cell wall is described by:

$$\rho_m \cdot V_m \cdot c_m \cdot \frac{dT_m}{dt} = -\Delta\dot{Q}_{mj} + \Delta\dot{Q}_{im} \quad (13)$$

The heat transfer within the i, j cell, assuming no fouling effects, is expressed as:

$$\Delta\dot{Q}_{im} = h_c \cdot (T_i - T_{mij}) \cdot \Delta A_{i,j} \quad (14)$$

$$\Delta\dot{Q}_{mj} = h_b \cdot (T_{mij} - T_j) \cdot \Delta A_{i,j} \quad (15)$$

The following equations represent the mass balance for „i” and „j” cells:

$$\frac{dN_i^L}{dt} = \dot{N}_{i-1}^L - \dot{N}_i^L + \frac{\Delta\dot{Q}_{im}}{B_i} \quad (16)$$

$$\frac{dN_j^L}{dt} = \dot{N}_{j-1}^L - \dot{N}_j^L - \frac{\Delta\dot{Q}_{mj}}{B_j} \quad (17)$$

$$\frac{dN_i^V}{dt} = \dot{N}_{i+1}^V - \dot{N}_i^V - \frac{\Delta\dot{Q}_{im}}{B_i} \quad (18)$$

$$\frac{dN_j^V}{dt} = \dot{N}_{j-1}^V - \dot{N}_j^V + \frac{\Delta\dot{Q}_{mj}}{B_j} \quad (19)$$

The mathematical model assumes that the vapour and liquid phases are in thermodynamic equilibrium, as described by to Eq. (8) and Eq. (9); the steady-state mass balance is also a fundamental assumption. Initially, equations (14)-(15) and (16)-(19) were incorporated into the energy balance equations, Eqs. (12)-(13). These combined equations were then linearised and subjected to a Laplace transformation for further analysis.

The operator transmittances for ten individual cells were interconnected through signal pathways, establishing a comprehensive relationship among them. A block diagram representing this interconnected system illustrates the dynamic structure and behaviour of the tested HME model. The block diagram shown in Figure 6 provides a visual tool for understanding the interaction of transmittances across the system’s various components. Based on the distinct signals of the variables coming into and going out of the apparatus, the HME dynamic model [22] was constructed. Figure 6 displays the model of two nearby cells, “i” and

"j". Block no. 1 in Figure 6, which represents the transmittances from G1 to G16, represents the first interaction associated with energy exchange. The transfer functions from G17 to G28 (block no. 2 in Figure 6) illustrate the mass exchange. Lastly, the impact of pressure on the apparatus dynamics—transmittances from G29 to G32 in block 3 of Figure 6—was considered. A cell's output signals serve as input signals to the cells that follow it.

Figure 6. Block diagram details for “i, j” cell [22].

The energy balance of a control volume is used to create the equation that characterises the dynamic behaviour of the rectifying R2 section (see Figure 7, where the control volume is considered to be the whole rectifying R2 section volume in column C2 – lumped parameter model).

The energy accumulation within the control volume is determined by the difference between the energy carried by the incoming fluid and the energy carried away by the outgoing fluid:

$$M_{R2} \cdot c_{R20} \cdot \frac{dT_{R20}}{dt} = \dot{m}_{R2}^V \cdot (c_{R2i}^V \cdot T_{R2i}^V + r_{R2i}^V) + \dot{m}_{R2} \cdot c_{R2}^L \cdot T_{Cs0} - \dot{m}_{R2}^L \cdot c_{R20}^L \cdot T_{R20} - \dot{m}_{CS} \cdot (c_{R20}^V \cdot T_{R20} + r_{R20}^V) \quad (20)$$

The dynamic model of the rectifying R2 section for distillation column C2 was constructed by isolating the signals corresponding to variables entering and exiting the apparatus, as depicted in Figure 7a. Initially, the interactions associated with energy transfer, as defined by Eq. (20), were analysed to determine the transmittances ranging from $G_{R2,1}$ to $G_{R2,4}$. Additionally, the model incorporated the effects of pressure on the apparatus’s dynamic behaviour, represented by the transmittance $G_{R2,5}$.

Figure 7. The block diagram for the dynamic model: a) of the rectifying R2 section for distillation column C2, b) of the condenser with the pressure controller.

The equations governing the condenser's dynamic behaviour are derived based on the energy balance within a defined control volume, as illustrated in Figure 7. The control volume encompasses the entire condenser, modelled as a lumped parameter system. The energy accumulation within this control volume is determined by subtracting the energy leaving the system through the outflowing fluid and heat transfer from the energy entering the system through the inflowing fluid. Heat transfer can occur into or out of the control volume via convection. This energy balance is mathematically expressed through three ordinary differential equations (assuming in the condenser $T_{Csi}=T_{Cso}$), (23), (24), and (25), which account for the energy exchanges in the tube-side fluid, the tube walls, and the shell-side fluid, respectively [28].

$$\frac{dT_{Cto}}{dt} = a_{C1} \cdot \dot{m}_{Ct} \cdot (T_{Cti} - T_{Cto}) + a_{C2} \cdot (T_{Cm} - T_{Cto}) \quad (23)$$

$$\frac{dT_{Cm}}{dt} = a_{C3} \cdot (T_{Cto} - T_{Cm}) + a_{C4} \cdot (T_{Cso} - T_{Cm}) \quad (24)$$

$$\frac{dT_{Cso}}{dt} = a_{C5} \cdot \dot{m}_{Cs} + a_{C6} \cdot (T_{Cm} - T_{Cso}) \quad (25)$$

where constants a_{C1} - a_{C6} are defined as follows:

$$a_{C1} = \frac{1}{\rho_{Ct} \cdot V_{Ct}}, \quad a_{C2} = \frac{n_C \cdot \pi \cdot d_{C1} \cdot l_C \cdot h_{Ctz}}{\rho_{Ct} \cdot c_{Ct} \cdot V_{Ct}}, \quad a_{C3} = \frac{n_C \cdot \pi \cdot d_{C1} \cdot l_C \cdot h_{Ctz}}{\rho_{Cm} \cdot c_{Cm} \cdot V_{Cm}},$$

$$a_{C4} = \frac{n_C \cdot \pi \cdot d_{C2} \cdot l_C \cdot h_{Csz}}{\rho_{Cm} \cdot c_{Cm} \cdot V_{Cm}}, \quad a_{C5} = \frac{r_{Cs}}{\rho_{Cs} \cdot c_{Cs} \cdot V_{Cs}}, \quad a_{C6} = \frac{n_C \cdot \pi \cdot d_{C2} \cdot l_C \cdot h_{Csz}}{\rho_{Cs} \cdot c_{Cs} \cdot V_{Cs}},$$

The impact of fouling on heat transfer within the condenser is accounted for because heat transfer coefficients are calculated using formulas that incorporate the thermal resistances contributed by fouling layers on both the tube-side and shell-side:

$$h_{Ctz} = \frac{h_{Ct}}{h_{Ct} \cdot R_{fCt} + 1}, \quad h_{CSz} = \frac{h_{Cs}}{h_{Cs} \cdot R_{fCs} + 1} \quad (26), (27)$$

The mathematical model for the condenser, governed by equations (23)–(25), enables the determination of relationships using operator transmittances. These relationships link disturbances at the model's inlet with resulting temperature changes at the outlet, as illustrated in Figure 7b. The initial interactions associated with energy exchange, represented by the transmittances G_{C1} , G_{C2} , G_{C3} , and G_{C5} , were analysed. Additionally, the model includes the influence of pressure on the condenser's dynamic behaviour, described by the transmittance G_{C4} .

The equation that characterises the dynamic behaviour of the stripping section, S1, is developed based on the energy balance within a defined control volume. As depicted in Figure 8, the control volume encompasses the entire S1 stripping section within column C1, modelled using a lumped parameter approach. The energy balance assumes that the energy accumulated in the control volume is equivalent to the difference between the energy brought in by the inflowing fluid and the energy removed by the outflowing fluid, according to Eq. (28). The mathematical tool so created facilitates understanding the thermodynamic dynamics of the stripping section and its role in the overall column operation.

$$M_{S1} \cdot c_{S10} \cdot \frac{dT_{S10}}{dt} = \dot{m}_{S1}^L \cdot c_{S1}^L \cdot T_{R10}^L + \dot{m}_{Rt} \cdot (c_{Rto} \cdot T_{Rto} + r_{Rto}) - \dot{m}_{S1}^V \cdot (c_{S10}^V \cdot T_{S10} + r_{S10}^V) - \dot{m}_{S10}^L \cdot c_{S10}^L \cdot T_{S10} \quad (28)$$

Figure 8. The block diagram for the dynamic model: a) of the stripping S1 section for distillation column C1, b) of the reboiler with the temperature controller.

The dynamic model of the stripping S1 section for distillation column C1 was developed by isolating the signals corresponding to the variables entering and exiting the apparatus, as depicted in Figure 8a. Initial analyses focused on energy exchange interactions, described by Eq. (28), which define the transmittances ranging from $G_{S1,1}$ to $G_{S1,4}$. Furthermore, the effect of pressure on the apparatus's dynamic behaviour was incorporated into the model through the transmittance $G_{S1,5}$. This comprehensive approach ensures that the model accurately captures the system's dynamic characteristics.

The dynamic behaviour of the reboiler is described using equations derived from the energy balance within a designated control volume, as illustrated in Figure 8. In this model, the control volume represents the entire reboiler, treated as a lumped parameter system. The energy accumulated in this volume is determined by subtracting the energy leaving through the outflowing fluid and the heat transferred out by convection (or adding heat transferred in) from the energy entering the inflowing fluid. This energy balance is mathematically formulated using three ordinary differential equations (assuming in the reboiler $T_{Rti}=T_{Rto}$) - Eqs. (29)-(31). These equations specifically address the energy balances for the tube-side fluid, the tube walls, and the shell-side fluid, respectively [28]:

$$\frac{dT_{Rto}}{dt} = a_{R1} \cdot \dot{m}_{Rt} + a_{R2} \cdot (T_{Rm} - T_{Rto}) \quad (29)$$

$$\frac{dT_{Rm}}{dt} = a_{R3} \cdot (T_{Rto} - T_{Rm}) + a_{R4} \cdot (T_{Rso} - T_{Rm}) \quad (30)$$

$$\frac{dT_{Rso}}{dt} = a_{R5} \cdot \dot{m}_{Rs} \cdot (T_{Rsi} - T_{Rso}) + a_{R6} \cdot (T_{Rm} - T_{Rso}) \quad (31)$$

where constants a_{R1} - a_{R6} are defined as follows:

$$a_{R1} = -\frac{r_{Rt}}{\rho_{Rt} \cdot c_{Rt} \cdot V_{Rt} \cdot (1 - \alpha_{Rt})}, \quad a_{R2} = \frac{n_R \cdot \pi \cdot d_{R1} \cdot l_R \cdot h_{Rtz}}{\rho_{Rt} \cdot c_{Rt} \cdot V_{Rt} \cdot (1 - \alpha_{Rt})}, \quad a_{R3} = \frac{n_R \cdot \pi \cdot d_{R1} \cdot l_R \cdot h_{Rtz}}{\rho_{Rm} \cdot c_{Rm} \cdot V_{Rm}},$$

$$a_{R4} = \frac{n_R \cdot \pi \cdot d_{R2} \cdot l_R \cdot h_{RSZ}}{\rho_{Rm} \cdot c_{Rm} \cdot V_{Rm}}, \quad a_{R5} = \frac{1}{\rho_{Rs} \cdot V_{Rs}}, \quad a_{R6} = \frac{n_R \cdot \pi \cdot d_{R2} \cdot l_R \cdot h_{RSZ}}{\rho_{Rs} \cdot c_{Rs} \cdot V_{Rs}},$$

Heat transfer coefficients accounting for the impact of fouling on heat transfer in the reboiler are calculated using equations that incorporate the thermal resistances of fouling layers on both the tube-side and shell-side, according to Eqs. (32) and (33). These resistances significantly influence the overall efficiency of heat exchange.

$$h_{Rtz} = \frac{h_{Rt}}{h_{Rt} \cdot R_{fRt+1}}, \quad h_{RSZ} = \frac{h_{Rs}}{h_{Rs} \cdot R_{fRs+1}} \quad (32), (33)$$

Relationships involving operator transmittances are established by solving Eqs. (29)–(31) in the reboiler's mathematical model, linking inlet disturbances to temperature variations at the outlet, as illustrated in Figure 8b. The initial interactions concerning energy transfer, represented by the transmittances G_{R1} , G_{R2} , G_{R3} , and G_{R5} , were determined. Additionally, the model incorporates the effects of pressure on the reboiler's dynamic response, captured through the transmittance G_{R4} .

2.2. Offset-free implicit tube model predictive control

Given an Uncertain Linear Time-Invariant (ULTI) system represented by the equation:

$$\mathbf{x}(t + T_s) = \mathbf{A}\mathbf{x}(t) + \mathbf{B}\mathbf{u}(t) + \mathbf{E}\mathbf{w}(t) \quad (34)$$

where t denotes the time sample in the discrete-time domain with a sampling time T_s . $\mathbf{A} \in \mathbb{R}^{n_x \times n_x}$ is the system matrix, $\mathbf{B} \in \mathbb{R}^{n_x \times n_u}$ is the input matrix, and the matrix pair (\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{B}) is stabilisable. $\mathbf{x}_k \in \mathbb{R}^{n_x}$ is a vector of state variables, $\mathbf{u}_k \in \mathbb{R}^{n_u}$ is a vector of input variables, $\mathbf{E} \in \mathbb{R}^{n_x \times n_w}$ is the disturbance matrix, and $\mathbf{w} \in \mathbb{W} \subset \mathbb{R}^{n_x}$ is a bounded vector of uncertain parameters, where \mathbb{W} is a compact set that includes the origin. The ULTI system (34) is considered to be constrained by

$$\mathbf{x}(t) \in \mathbb{X}, \mathbf{u}(t) \in \mathbb{U}, \forall t \geq 0, \quad (35)$$

where $\mathbb{X} \subseteq \mathbb{R}^{n_x}$ and $\mathbb{U} \subseteq \mathbb{R}^{n_u}$ are polytopes containing the origin in their strict interiors. To assure offset-free reference tracking, the model in (34) is augmented by an integral action in a conventional way, such that

$$\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_k = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{x}_k \\ \mathbf{x}_{i,k} \end{bmatrix} \quad (36)$$

is the augmented vector of state variables, where $\mathbf{x}_{i,k} \in \mathbb{R}^{n_y}$ denotes the integral action member defined as $\mathbf{x}_{i,k} = \sum_{i=0}^k (\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{y}_k)$ with $\mathbf{y}_k \in \mathbb{R}^{n_y}$ being a control output and $\mathbf{r} \in \mathbb{R}^{n_y}$ being the reference value.

Subsequently, the matrices of the augmented state-space model are defined as

$$\tilde{\mathbf{A}} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{A} & \mathbf{0} \\ -T_s \mathbf{C} & \mathbf{I} \end{bmatrix}, \tilde{\mathbf{B}} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{B} \\ \mathbf{0} \end{bmatrix}, \tilde{\mathbf{C}} = [\mathbf{C} \quad \mathbf{0}]. \quad (37)$$

The convex set is referred to as a ‘‘tube’’ $\mathbb{T} \subset \mathbb{R}^{n_x}$ is created as an invariant approximation of the minimal robust positively invariant set, following the algorithm outlined in [29].

The conventional tube MPC design problem is in the form:

$$\begin{aligned} \min_{\hat{\mathbf{u}}_0, \dots, \hat{\mathbf{u}}_{N-1}, \hat{\mathbf{x}}_0, \dots, \hat{\mathbf{x}}_N} \quad & \|\hat{\mathbf{x}}_N\|_{\mathbf{P}}^2 + \sum_{k=0}^{N-1} (\|\hat{\mathbf{x}}_k\|_{\mathbf{Q}}^2 + \|\hat{\mathbf{u}}_k\|_{\mathbf{R}}^2) \\ \text{s.t.:} \quad & \tilde{\mathbf{x}}(t) - \hat{\mathbf{x}}_0 \in \mathbb{T}, \\ & \hat{\mathbf{x}}_{k+1} = \tilde{\mathbf{A}}\hat{\mathbf{x}}_k + \tilde{\mathbf{B}}\hat{\mathbf{u}}_k, \\ & \hat{\mathbf{x}}_k \in \mathbb{X} \ominus \mathbb{T}, \\ & \hat{\mathbf{u}}_k \in \mathbb{U} \ominus K \cdot \mathbb{T}, \\ & \hat{\mathbf{x}}_N \in \mathbb{X}_N, \end{aligned} \quad (38)$$

for all steps $\forall k = 0, \dots, N - 1$ for the prediction horizon N . The quadratic objective function in equation (38) is minimised considering the penalty matrices $\mathbf{Q} \in \mathbb{R}^{n_x \times n_x}$, $\mathbf{R} \in \mathbb{R}^{n_u \times n_u}$, and $\mathbf{P} \in \mathbb{R}^{n_x \times n_x}$ are set such that $\mathbf{Q} \succcurlyeq \mathbf{0}$, $\mathbf{R} \succ \mathbf{0}$, and $\mathbf{P} \succ \mathbf{0}$ hold. The penalty matrix \mathbf{Q} comprises 2 parts, i.e., the partial matrix $\mathbf{Q}_x \in \mathbb{R}^{n_x \times n_x}$ penalising the original vector of system states \mathbf{x}_k and the matrix $\mathbf{Q}_i \in \mathbb{R}^{n_i \times n_i}$ penalising the integral action member $\mathbf{x}_{i,k}$:

$$\mathbf{Q} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{Q}_x & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{Q}_i \end{bmatrix}. \quad (39)$$

Vectors $\hat{\mathbf{u}}_k$ and $\hat{\mathbf{x}}_k$ are decision variables optimised concerning the nominal Linear Time-Invariant (LTI) system $\hat{\mathbf{x}}_{k+1} = \tilde{\mathbf{A}}\hat{\mathbf{x}}_k + \tilde{\mathbf{B}}\hat{\mathbf{u}}_k$, without considering any uncertain parameters \mathbf{w} . The initial condition $\tilde{\mathbf{x}}(t) - \hat{\mathbf{x}}_0 \in \mathbb{T}$ considers the ‘‘tube’’ \mathbb{T} to ensure that the perturbed system state vector $\tilde{\mathbf{x}}(t)$ remains close to its nominal counterpart $\hat{\mathbf{x}}_0$. Similarly, the state and input

constraints in equation (35) are adjusted to respect the robust positive invariant set \mathbb{T} , assuming that $\mathbb{X} \ominus \mathbb{T}$ and $\mathbb{U} \ominus \mathbf{K} \mathbb{T}$ are non-empty sets and convex by definition, with \mathbf{K} representing the Linear Quadratic Regulator - LQR gain.

The control action $u(t)$, applied to the ULTI (34), is determined by the control law $\boldsymbol{\kappa} : \mathbb{X}_F \rightarrow \mathbb{U}$ as follows:

$$\boldsymbol{\kappa}(\mathbf{x}(t)) = \hat{\mathbf{u}}_0^* + \mathbf{K}(\tilde{\mathbf{x}}(t) - \hat{\mathbf{x}}_0^*), \quad (40)$$

where $\hat{\mathbf{u}}_0^*$ and $\hat{\mathbf{x}}_0^*$ are solutions to the optimisation problem in equation (38), and $\mathbb{X}_F \subseteq \mathbb{R}^{n_x}$, the feasibility set of the optimised initial condition $\hat{\mathbf{x}}_0^*$, is the domain. The tube MPC is implemented in a receding horizon fashion, meaning that only the first control action, $\mathbf{u}(t) = \boldsymbol{\kappa}(\mathbf{x}(t))$, is applied to the plant, and then the optimisation problem is re-computed at each control step, considering the current measurements as the initial condition.

From the control strategy described above, it is clear that performing several set-based operations is necessary to construct the tube and handle the constraints of the optimisation problem. For this reason, implementing the tube MPC is challenging for complex systems. To avoid these set-based operations, the implicit tube MPC setup algorithm, introduced in [30], transforms the original robust positive invariant set \mathbb{T} into a corresponding implicit form $\boldsymbol{\tau} \in \mathbb{R}^{n_x}$ defined as

$$\boldsymbol{\tau} = (1 - \alpha)^{-1} \sum_{j=0}^{N_S-1} (\tilde{\mathbf{A}} + \tilde{\mathbf{B}}\mathbf{K})^j \boldsymbol{\omega}_j, \quad (41)$$

where

$$\mathbf{e}_i^\top \boldsymbol{\omega}_j \leq 1, i = 1, \dots, N_W, j = 1, \dots, N_S. \quad (42)$$

The sequence of uncertainties $\boldsymbol{\omega}$ is translated from the original uncertain parameters \mathbf{w} . This sequence corresponds to the iterative procedure of tube construction, having N_S steps, i.e., $\boldsymbol{\omega}_j \in \mathbb{R}^{n_x}$ for $j = 1, \dots, N_S$. However, the tube geometry is not explicitly constructed using the implicit approach. Instead, the optimised vectors $\boldsymbol{\omega}$ from the original set \mathbb{W} are considered, influenced by N_S steps of the dynamics $(\tilde{\mathbf{A}} + \tilde{\mathbf{B}}\mathbf{K})$, leading to specific vertices of the original tube \mathbb{T} . Therefore, the original initial condition in equation (38) changes to the equality form:

$$\mathbf{x}(t) - \hat{\mathbf{x}}_0 = \boldsymbol{\tau} \quad (43)$$

Additionally, the implicit tube $\boldsymbol{\tau}$ is projected to the constraints using a vector $\mathbf{f} \in \mathbb{R}^{N_C}$, so that the following statements are equivalent:

$$\begin{aligned} (\hat{\mathbf{x}}_k \times \hat{\mathbf{u}}_k) &\in ((\mathbb{X} \ominus \mathbb{T}) \times (\mathbb{U} \ominus \mathbf{K} \cdot \mathbb{T})), \\ \mathbf{c}_l^\top \hat{\mathbf{x}}_k + \mathbf{d}_l^\top \hat{\mathbf{u}}_k &\leq 1 - \mathbf{f}_l, l = 1, \dots, N_C. \end{aligned} \quad (44)$$

The vector $\mathbf{f} \in \mathbb{R}^{N_C}$, constructed offline, represents the implicit tube projection into the state and input constraints, effectively reducing the volume of the original sets \mathbb{X} and \mathbb{U} . The vector \mathbf{f} is given by:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{f}_l &= (1 - \alpha)^{-1} \sum_{j=0}^{N_S-1} h\left(\mathbb{W}, ((\tilde{\mathbf{A}} + \tilde{\mathbf{B}}\mathbf{K})^j)^\top \boldsymbol{\eta}_l\right), \\ \boldsymbol{\eta}_l &= \mathbf{c}_l + \mathbf{K}^\top \mathbf{d}_l, l = 1, \dots, N_C. \end{aligned} \quad (45)$$

Similarly, using the vector \mathbf{f} , the terminal constraint is reformulated:

$$\mathbf{c}_l^\top \hat{\mathbf{x}}_k + \mathbf{d}_l^\top \hat{\mathbf{u}}_k \leq 1 - \mathbf{f}_l, l = 1, \dots, N_C. \quad (46)$$

Since the evaluation of the implicit tube $\boldsymbol{\tau}$ and the vector \mathbf{f} does not include the Minkowski sum operation, the original tube MPC in equation (38) is for the implicit tube MPC setup according to [30] transformed into a convex programming problem in the form

$$\begin{aligned} \min_{\hat{\mathbf{u}}_0, \hat{\mathbf{x}}_0, \boldsymbol{\omega}_0, \dots, \hat{\mathbf{u}}_{N-1}, \hat{\mathbf{x}}_N, \boldsymbol{\omega}_{N_S}} \quad & \|\hat{\mathbf{x}}_N\|_P^2 + \sum_{k=0}^{N-1} (\|\hat{\mathbf{x}}_k\|_Q^2 + \|\hat{\mathbf{u}}_k\|_R^2) \\ \text{s.t.:} \quad & \tilde{\mathbf{x}}(t) - \hat{\mathbf{x}}_0 = \boldsymbol{\tau}, \\ & \mathbf{e}_i^\top \boldsymbol{\omega}_j \leq 1, \\ & \hat{\mathbf{x}}_{k+1} = \tilde{\mathbf{A}}\hat{\mathbf{x}}_k + \tilde{\mathbf{B}}\hat{\mathbf{u}}_k, \\ & \mathbf{c}_l^\top \hat{\mathbf{x}}_k + \mathbf{d}_l^\top \hat{\mathbf{u}}_k \leq 1 - \mathbf{f}_l, \\ & (\mathbf{c}_l^\top + \mathbf{d}_l^\top \mathbf{K})\hat{\mathbf{x}}_N \leq 1 - \mathbf{f}_l, \\ & i = 1, \dots, N_W, \\ & j = 1, \dots, N_S, \\ & k = 0, \dots, N - 1, \\ & l = 1, \dots, N_C, \end{aligned} \quad (47)$$

while the control law remains in the form defined in equation (40).

The implicit tube MPC involves N_S optimisation variables more than the original tube MPC due to the additional sequence $\boldsymbol{\omega}$. However, the implicit formulation avoids restricting tube MPC to control problems in simple geometry and enables real-time tuning of the performance criteria.

3. Results and discussion

The repository [31] contains research data corresponding to the simulation results discussed in this section, which validates the study's findings. It also includes code, models, algorithms, and other valuable materials associated with the project. Before developing the computer-aided dynamic model, a thorough block diagram of the HHIDiS system should be created to visualise the interdependencies between model components.

The entire block structure of the HHIDiS system is quite complex, as it is envisioned as a group of various process equipment pieces connected as shown in Figure 3. Using Simulink software within a MATLAB environment, the block diagram of the HHIDiS system, as illustrated in Figure 9, can be implemented and transformed into a simulation tool. Establishing a database with the steady-state values of the operating parameters in each process equipment unit is required. The current study has accomplished this by computing thermal-flow parameters. To be more precise, the database contains the following information for every apparatus: mass and molar flows, heat transfer coefficients, thermal resistance due to fouling, geometrical parameters, and thermophysical properties of the fluids, such as densities, heat capacities, dynamic viscosities, and thermal conductivities.

Figure 9. A view of the developed Simulink block diagram of the HHIDiS system in accordance with Figure 3.

The steady-state mathematical model proposed by Markowski et al. [1] was used to determine thermal-flow calculations and the selection of geometric parameters for HME. The process flow diagram in Figure 2 was considered, where the calculated HME consists of rectifying R1 and stripping S2 sections. However, calculations for the classic distillation of the S1 stripping section of the C1 column and the R2 rectification section of the C2 column were carried out using the AspenHysys V11 software.

The following data were assumed, according to work [22]:

- feed: a mixture of propane and butane with 0.45 mole fraction of propane,
- molar flowrate of feed for C1 column: 490 kmol/h,
- molar flowrate of feed for C2 column: 510 kmol/h,
- mole fraction of propane in distillate: 0.99,
- mole fraction of propane in residue: 0.01,
- heating water temperature at inlet/outlet: 160/150 °C,
- cooling water temperature at inlet/outlet: 20/25 °C,
- pressure in the C1 distillation column: 2500 kPa,
- pressure in the C2 distillation column: 1000 kPa,

The number of theoretical mixing zones, equivalent to theoretical trays, and the column profiles were determined using equations (5)–(10). The calculation resulted in 100 theoretical mixing zones. Considering a tray efficiency of 0.6, the actual number of mixing zones was calculated to be 167. The column profiles, adapted from reference [22], are symbolically depicted in Figure 4b. Furthermore, a minimum temperature difference of 3 K was assumed between the column profiles (sections R1 and S2) in the temperature-enthalpy (T-H) diagram.

The geometrical parameters of HME were calculated using Eqs. (1)-(4). The channel geometry (Z-type channel as in work [27]) and the apparatus dimensions are the following [22]:

- heat transfer area of 918 m²,
- plate size 1.8 m x 2.05 m (3.7 m²),
- 10 mm clearance between plates,
- No. of plates: 248.

Then, thermal-flow calculations for the reboiler of the C1 column and the condenser of the C2 column (see Figure 10) were carried out using the HTRI Xchanger Suite 7.3.2 software. The obtained results are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Calculation parameters for the shell-and-tube heat exchangers: reboiler and condenser.

Exchanger classification by the Tubular Exchanger Manufacturers Association - TEMA	Reboiler	Condenser
Internal diameter of the shell, mm	1000	1200
Tube length, m	3.6	8
Number of tubes	773	1131
Number of tube passes	1	2
Outside diameter (OD) of tubes, mm	25.4	25.4
Thickness of tube wall, mm	2.11	2.11
Tube pitch, mm	32	32
Layout	30°	30°
Baffle spacing, mm	600	600
Baffle cut % diameter	30	35
Type of baffle	Single segmental	Single segmental
Clearances	TEMA standards	TEMA standards
Flow rate on the tube side, kg/s	55.6 (butane)	224.57 (cooling water)
Flow rate on the shell side, kg/s	111.97 (heating water)	14.48 (propane)
Pressure on the tube side, kPa	2500 (butane)	500 (cooling water)
Pressure on the shell side, kPa	700 (heating water)	1100 (propane)
Temperature at inlet/outlet, °C	160/150 (heating water)	20/25 (cooling water)
Temperature at inlet/outlet, °C	130.6/130.3 (butane)	31.25/30.85 (propane)
Duty, MW	4.8437	4.6988
Effective heat transfer area, m ²	211.48	712.25
Actual overall heat transfer coefficient, W/m ² K	1054.6	843.0
Effective mean temperature difference EMTD, °C	24.2	8.2

Figure 10. The assumed geometry details of the reboiler, coupled with column C1 – (a), and the condenser, coupled with column C2 – (b).

3.1. Control objectives

This case study aims to implement the offset-free implicit tube MPC framework for HHIDiS models affected by fouling. The closed-loop control performance was investigated using extensive numerical analyses. The control profiles and quality criteria were evaluated in relation

to the well-tuned PID controllers. From the control viewpoint, the pressure in the condenser (P_j) and temperature in the reboiler (T_{Rto}) as Controlled Variables (CV). The associated Manipulated Variables (MV) are the mass flow rate of cooling water in the condenser (m_{ct}) and the mass flow rate of heating water in the reboiler (m_{rs}).

Varying fouling levels significantly affect the dynamic behaviour of the HHIDiS by decreasing the heat-transfer capability, thus changing the system parameters. Such changes progressively degrade the accuracy of the underlying process model. Conventional PID controllers, typically tuned for a fixed operating point, cannot adapt to these gradual variations in system behaviour caused by fouling. Consequently, the control performance of PID controllers tends to deteriorate over time. In contrast, the offset-free implicit tube MPC framework implemented in this study explicitly addresses uncertainties in the model and accounts for changes in parameters caused by fouling through repetitive real-time optimisation at each control step. This framework ensures enhanced closed-loop control performance and robustness, particularly under conditions of significant fouling, which is a crucial aspect for industrially relevant applications. While previous studies, such as [20] and [21], have explored PID-based control strategies for HIDiCs, this case study implements MPC, enabling real-time optimisation of control performance under system constraints. By integrating the offset-free implicit tube MPC framework, this work improves control performance and effectively handles dynamic disturbances caused by fouling. Additionally, compared to the centralised and distributed MPC frameworks analysed in [23], which focus on architectural design, our control strategy specifically incorporates changing system parameters affected by fouling as an additive disturbance. As a consequence, its impact on system behaviour decreases over time. This tailored control approach enhances robustness while maintaining computational efficiency. Finally, in contrast to the offset-free robust MPC method based on Linear Matrix Inequalities (LMI) proposed in [25], which is computationally intensive, the proposed offset-free implicit tube MPC minimises computational effort and, consequently, increases the implementation range of the proposed control approach.

Figure 11. The control scheme of offset-free tube MPC.

Two main tasks were investigated for each controlled variable: (i) the reference tracking and (ii) the regulatory problems. Figure 11 depicts the simplified control scheme of the implemented control policy. The performance of the designed MPC strategy is studied by considering two control scenarios, as shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Considered control scenarios.

	Control scenario I	Control scenario II
Reference step change (P_j) [Pa]	0 → 1000 (reference tracking)	0 → 0 (regulatory problem)
Reference step change (T_{Rto}) [°C]	0 → 0 (regulatory problem)	0 → 0.1 (reference tracking)

These scenarios are performed to study both reference tracking and disturbance rejection control problems. Moreover, both of these control scenarios are considered with 4 different levels of fouling recommended by Tubular Exchanger Manufacturers Association (TEMA) standards [32]: clean (R_{f0}), low (R_{f1}), medium (R_{f2}), and high fouling (R_{f3}), see Table 3. The offset-free tube MPC is compared with well-tuned PID controllers, adopting the conventional control performance criteria for each control scenario. These include Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) and maximum overshoot (σ_{MAX}), as well as the carbon footprint related to the fuel oil combustion while preheating the heating water in the reboiler and the corresponding price of the fuel oil.

Table 3. Values of the R_f parameter according to TEMA standards.

Exchanger	Fouling parameter $R_f \cdot 10^{-4}$ (m ² K/W)			
	R_{f0} clean	R_{f1} low fouling	R_{f2} medium fouling	R_{f3} high fouling
HME exchanger				
R1 section “i” – propane/butane mixture	0	0.9	1.8	2.34
S2 section “j” – propane/butane mixture	0	0.9	1.8	2.34
Condenser				
shell side – propane	0	0.9	1.8	2.34
tube side – cooling water	0	0.9	2.5	4.5
Reboiler				
shell side – butane	0	0.9	1.8	2.34
tube side – heating water	0	0.9	1.8	2.34

3.2. Control setup

The closed-loop control performances analysed in the extensive case study were obtained using the MATLAB/Simulink R2023b programming environment on a CPU with an i5-1.7 GHz processor and 16 GB of RAM. The implicit tube MPC was constructed using the MPTplus [33]. Optimisation problems were parsed using the YALMIP R20210331 toolbox [34] with MOSEK 10.0.40 [35] as a solver.

The PID Tuner App in Simulink was applied to tuning the PID controllers, and the parameters are listed in Table 4. The considered transfer function of the PID controllers is formulated as follows:

$$G_C(s) = K_P + \frac{K_I}{s} + K_D s \quad (48)$$

where K_P is the proportional, K_I is the integral and K_D is the derivative gain, and s is the Laplace operator. The well-tuned PID controllers provide satisfactory control performance; however, the control inputs were optimised neither to account for input and output constraints nor to be subject to system uncertainties. Implementation of robust MPC directly addressed these requirements.

Table 4. PID controllers parameters.

Tuning parameters	PID controller of condenser	PID controller of reboiler
K_P	$-9.5 \cdot 10^{-3}$	1.80
K_I	$-5.3 \cdot 10^{-4}$	0.97
K_D	0	0

Considering the augmented state-space model in (37) and the uncertain state-space model in (34), the offset-free tube MPC was designed taking into consideration the discrete-time state-space model of the condenser in the form

$$\widetilde{\mathbf{A}}_C = \begin{bmatrix} 0.9598 & 0 \\ 1 & 1 \end{bmatrix}, \widetilde{\mathbf{B}}_C = \begin{bmatrix} -2.2579 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}, \mathbf{E}_C = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}, \quad (49)$$

and the model of the reboiler is as follows

$$\widetilde{\mathbf{A}}_R = \begin{bmatrix} 0.9435 & 0 \\ 1 & 1 \end{bmatrix}, \widetilde{\mathbf{B}}_R = \begin{bmatrix} 0.6053 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}, \mathbf{E}_R = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (50)$$

considering the sampling time $T_S = 0.1$ s. The bound on the uncertain parameters \mathbf{w} in equation (34) was determined based on the effect of fouling and the impact of nonlinearities, assuming $w_{\max} = 34$ for the condenser and $w_{\max} = 6 \cdot 10^{-3}$ for the reboiler.

Constraints on the control inputs \mathbf{u} in deviation form are set to meet the physical limits of the manipulated variable and are in the form

$$-v^s \leq \mathbf{u} \leq 2 \cdot v^s, \quad (51)$$

where v^s denotes the steady-state value of the manipulated variable being $v^s = m_{ct}^s = 224.57$ kg/s for the condenser and $v^s = m_{rs}^s = 111.97$ kg/s. In industrial implementations, it is essential to ensure the safe control of the plant, so constraints on system states are also implemented. For the condenser, the constraint on the state variable \mathbf{x} is defined as

$$-5000 \leq \mathbf{x}_C \leq 5000, \quad (52)$$

and for the reboiler, the constraint is in the form

$$-2 \leq \mathbf{x}_R \leq 2, \quad (53)$$

The above constraints on the system states represent safety margins for the pressure and temperature, respectively. Without loss of generality, the integral action of the augmented system's state vector was formally unconstrained.

Fine-tuning of the parameters of the tube MPC design problem in equation (38) was achieved by modifying the penalty matrices \mathbf{Q} and \mathbf{R} and by the prediction horizon length N . The length of the prediction horizon was set to sufficiently predict the system dynamics, leading to a value of $N = 200$. The selected subset of the investigated settings of the penalty \mathbf{Q} and \mathbf{R} are listed in Table 5. Note the value of the penalty \mathbf{Q}_x directly tunes the aggressiveness of the tuned controllers and is analogous to the tuning of the proportional gain of the PID controller. Analogously, the matrix \mathbf{Q}_i is a penalty on the integral action ensuring that the control performance is offset-free.

The controllers shown in Table 5 were tuned with two primary objectives: to improve control performance and reduce heating water consumption in the reboiler. This reduction results in a lower carbon footprint and lower fuel oil costs for water preheating.

Table 5. Analysed control setups for the condenser and reboiler tube MPC.

Control setup	Tube MPC of condenser			Tube MPC of reboiler		
	\mathbf{Q}_x	\mathbf{Q}_i	$\mathbf{R} \cdot 10^6$	\mathbf{Q}_x	$\mathbf{Q}_i \cdot 10^6$	$\mathbf{R} \cdot 10^6$
A	75	0.3	1	5	0.1	0.5
B	75	0.5	1	5	0.1	0.5
C	113	0.2	1	5	2	0.5
D	50	0.2	1	5	2	0.5
E	150	5	1	5	0.1	0.5
F	113	0.415	1	5	2	0.5
G	113	0.6	1	5	2	0.5
H	75	0.5	1	5	2	0.5

3.3. Closed-loop control performance

The closed-loop control trajectories generated using the PID controller strategy and the designed tube MPC with control setups A and H for control scenario I are depicted in Figures 12 and 13. The system responses for control scenario II are presented in Figures 14 and 15. To improve control performance, tube MPC controllers were initially tuned aggressively (setups E–H in Table 5) with increased values of \mathbf{Q}_x and \mathbf{Q}_i leading to decreased settling times. In numerical analysis of the control performance, the RMSE criterion was evaluated as follows:

$$\text{RMSE} = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{j=1}^M (\mathbf{r}_j - \mathbf{y}_j)^2}{M}}, \quad (54)$$

where the term $(\mathbf{r}_j - \mathbf{y}_j)$ represents the control error in the considered control step and is defined as the difference between the reference \mathbf{r}_j and the controlled variable \mathbf{y}_j . Parameter M is the total number of evaluated control steps. As the RMSE criterion is based on the calculation of the control error, lower values indicate improved control performance (see Table 6). Robust MPC controllers demonstrated superior performance, achieving RMSE reductions up to 35% compared to conventional PID controllers.

Table 6. Values of the RMSE criterion for both control scenarios for all considered values of the R_f parameter.

Controller	Parameter R_f	Control scenario I		Control scenario II	
		RMSE(P_j)	RMSE(T_{Rto})	RMSE(P_j)	RMSE(T_{Rto})
PID controllers	R_{f0}	328.7	0.0058	525.8	0.0360
	R_{f1}	355.6	0.0059	431.5	0.0360
	R_{f2}	304.1	0.0049	402.9	0.0349
	R_{f3}	406.0	0.0071	374.4	0.0357
Tube MPC setup A	R_{f0}	257.5	0.0105	381.0	0.0465
	R_{f1}	236.5	0.0058	315.2	0.0415
	R_{f2}	238.7	0.0054	275.7	0.0396
	R_{f3}	308.9	0.0060	261.3	0.0391
Tube MPC setup H	R_{f0}	262.5	0.0075	411.4	0.0320
	R_{f1}	229.6	0.0047	324.9	0.0293
	R_{f2}	243.6	0.0045	280.4	0.0281
	R_{f3}	373.3	0.0053	266.8	0.0298

To provide a more intuitive comparison of RMSE values between the offset-free tube MPC setup and PID controllers, the relative improvement Δ_{RMSE} of these values was evaluated as a ratio given by

$$\Delta_{\text{RMSE}} = \frac{\text{RMSE}_{\text{MPC}} - \text{RMSE}_{\text{PID}}}{\text{RMSE}_{\text{PID}}} \cdot 100\%, \quad (55)$$

with RMSE_{MPC} evaluated using Eq. (54) for trajectories obtained using tube MPC controllers and RMSE_{PID} for PID controllers, respectively. Obviously, following the definition of the Δ_{RMSE} criterion, it is clear that negative values indicate better control performance of tube MPC relative to the PID controllers, and vice versa.

Figure 12. Closed-loop performance of control scenario I - reference tracking control problem: PID controller (purple solid), offset-free tube MPC setup A (green dash-dotted), and tube MPC setup H (orange dotted) for all considered values of the R_f parameter.

The values of the calculated Δ_{RMSE} criteria are listed in Table 7 for both control scenarios and the most promising tube MPC control setups A and H. The data are provided for all 4 studied levels of fouling, represented by the values of the R_f parameter, see Table 3.

Based on the results summarised in Table 7, considering the reference tracking problem, i.e., the control aimed at achieving the reference value of the temperature in the reboiler, the PID controller ensures better control performance in control scenario II compared to the tube MPC with control setup A.

Table 7. Values of the Δ_{RMSE} criterion for both control scenarios for all considered values of the R_f parameter.

Controller	Parameter R_f	Control scenario I		Control scenario II	
		$\Delta_{\text{RMSE}}(P_j)$ [%]	$\Delta_{\text{RMSE}}(T_{\text{Rto}})$ [%]	$\Delta_{\text{RMSE}}(P_j)$ [%]	$\Delta_{\text{RMSE}}(T_{\text{Rto}})$ [%]
Tube MPC setup A	R_{f0}	-21.67	81.13	-27.54	28.93
	R_{f1}	-33.48	-1.35	-26.96	15.43
	R_{f2}	-21.53	8.53	-31.58	13.52
	R_{f3}	-23.92	-15.22	-30.22	9.45
Tube MPC setup H	R_{f0}	-20.13	28.84	-21.76	-11.25
	R_{f1}	-35.44	-19.62	-24.71	-18.46
	R_{f2}	-19.91	-8.39	-30.41	-19.52

R_{f3}	-8.06	-24.97	-28.75	-16.60
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These results are also observable in Figure 15, where the tube MPC for the control setup A provided a slower control process. Similar behaviour can be observed in Figure 13, where the control trajectories of the disturbance rejection problem in control scenario I are shown. On the other hand, the tube MPC with the control setup A outperformed the PID controller in controlling the pressure in the condenser, i.e., in the reference tracking problem in control scenario I (Figure 12) and the disturbance rejection problem in control scenario II (Figure 14). The tube MPC setup H outperformed the PID controllers in all studied cases except for the control scenario I, with R_{f0} .

However, as the tube MPC setup H was tuned to be more aggressive, it provided an oscillatory control performance, especially with increasing fouling levels in the reference tracking problem of control scenario I. Figure 12 indicates that for R_{f2} and R_{f3} , the oscillations are higher than those obtained using the PID controller. More conservative tube controllers were tuned to achieve a less oscillating behaviour, i.e., the tube MPC for control setups A–D, as shown in Table 5. In Figures 12–15, it can be observed that the tube MPC setup A provided a more conservative control performance in all control cases, resulting in trajectories with damped oscillations compared to the other analysed controllers. To compare the oscillatory behaviour of the controllers, the maximum overshoot criterion σ_{MAX} was evaluated and defined as:

$$\sigma_{\text{MAX}} = \frac{\mathbf{y}_{\text{MAX}} - \mathbf{y}_{\infty}}{\mathbf{y}_{\infty} - \mathbf{y}_0} \cdot 100\%, \quad (56)$$

where \mathbf{y}_{MAX} and \mathbf{y}_{∞} are the maximal and steady-state values of the controlled variable, while \mathbf{y}_0 is its initial value. Since maximum overshoot can only be evaluated for reference tracking problems, it is not reasonably applicable in disturbance rejection scenarios. In this case, the goal is to maintain the controlled variable at its steady state, thereby avoiding division by zero that would be non-applicable. Given that the maximum values of the controlled variables are comparable in control scenario I (with the previously mentioned exception), Table 8 lists the maximum overshoot values only for the reference tracking problem in control scenario II.

Table 8. Maximum overshoot in temperature control (Control scenario II) for all considered values of the R_f parameter.

	Parameter R_f	PID controller	Tube MPC setup A	Tube MPC setup H
	R_{f0}	1.90	0	1.02
σ_{MAX} [%]	R_{f1}	4.71	0	0.28
	R_{f2}	8.25	0	3.14
	R_{f3}	11.81	0	5.33

Figure 13. Closed-loop performance of control scenario I – disturbance rejection control problem: PID controller (purple solid), offset-free tube MPC setup A (green dash-dotted), and tube MPC setup H (orange dotted) for all considered values of the R_f parameter.

Based on the results summarised in Table 8, tube MPC setup A achieved offset-free control without overshoots across all four levels of fouling. Additionally, the tube MPC setup H significantly reduced the maximum overshoot values compared to the PID controller for all levels of fouling while maintaining improved RMSE values.

The presented results demonstrate that the robust MPC tuning strategy has a substantial influence on the stability and operational efficiency of the controlled system. Aggressive, robust MPC tuning, as demonstrated by Setup H, significantly improved the system's responsiveness and control accuracy (lower RMSE) compared to conventional PID controllers across nearly all fouling conditions. However, this increased responsiveness introduces a trade-off, as observed from the oscillatory behaviour and higher maximum overshoot recognised at higher fouling levels (e.g., R_{f2} and R_{f3}). On the other hand, the conservatively tuned robust MPC setup A consistently achieved stable, offset-free performance without any overshoot, providing damped control trajectories under all investigated fouling scenarios. These results highlight the importance of careful selection between aggressive and conservative tuning approaches, depending on specific industrial preferences, i.e., whether prioritising fast response or operation with minimised overshoots.

Another goal of this case study is to analyse the carbon footprint and fuel oil costs related to preheating the heating water for the reboiler. First, the total amount of CO_2 emissions are given by:

$$m(\text{CO}_2) = m_{\text{RS,TOTAL}} \cdot c_p \cdot \Delta T \cdot e_{\text{CO}_2}, \quad (57)$$

where $m_{RS,TOTAL}$ is the total mass of heating water used during the entire control period, while $c_p = 4.19 \text{ kJ}/(\text{kg K})$ is the specific heat of water, $\Delta T = 10 \text{ K}$ is a temperature change during oil combustion. Analogously, a fuel oil price is defined as

$$\text{price(fuel oil)} = \frac{m_{RS,TOTAL} \cdot c_p \cdot \Delta T \cdot p}{\eta}, \quad (58)$$

Figure 14. Closed-loop performance of control scenario II – disturbance rejection control problem: PID controller (purple solid), offset-free tube MPC setup A (green dash-dotted), and tube MPC setup H (orange dotted) for all considered values of the R_f parameter.

where $p = 1.8 \cdot 10^{-5} \text{ USD/kJ}$ is the unit price of fuel oil, and $\eta = 0.85$ is furnace efficiency. The values of the carbon footprint for the analysed tube MPC control setups and PID controllers for all control cases are displayed in Figure 16, and the costs of the fuel oil are shown in Figure 17. In both, Figure a) shows the values for the control scenario I for all values of fouling, and Figure b) shows the values for the control scenario II. Here, in Figures denoted by a), it can be seen that the conservatively tuned tube MPC controllers (circles) were able to decrease the carbon footprint and the price of the fuel in lower levels of fouling, i.e., R_{f0} and R_{f1} , compared to PID controllers (dashed line). However, with increasing levels of fouling, the values are comparable to the values for the PID controller or slightly higher. On the other hand, the aggressively tuned tube MPCs provide increased values of the carbon footprint and the price of the fuel oil for the low levels of fouling and for the higher levels of fouling, i.e., R_{f2} and R_{f3} provided values close to the values of the PID controller.

On the contrary, in Figure b), it can be seen that tube MPC control setups A, B, and E significantly decreased the values for all levels of fouling compared to the PID controller, as they ensured lower consumption of the heating water in the reboiler. These generated results demonstrate that the robust MPC approach, particularly the conservative tuning setups, not only ensures reduced fuel oil costs compared to conventional PID controllers but also offers

significant control and operational benefits. From an economic perspective, selecting an appropriate robust MPC tuning strategy can significantly influence operational expenditures, especially in industrial-oriented scenarios, where fuel oil consumption represents a considerable portion of total operational costs.

The observed reductions in energy consumption and associated carbon emissions achieved by MPC can be intuitively linked to the structure of MPC itself. Specifically, MPC offers straightforward tuning via weighting matrices Q and R , enabling operators to directly penalise excessive control effort by increasing the value of the weighting matrix R . This intuitive tuning mechanism inherently promotes smoother control actions and consequently reduces unnecessary consumption of heating water, thus decreasing both energy demand and carbon footprint.

Figure 15. Closed-loop performance of control scenario II - reference tracking control problem: PID controller (purple solid), offset-free tube MPC setup A (green dash-dotted), and tube MPC setup H (orange dotted) for all considered values of the R_f parameter.

Figure 16. Comparison of CO₂ emissions of the heating medium over the entire control period for control setups of tube MPC (circles), summarised in Table 5 and PID controller (dashed):
a) control scenario I, b) control scenario II.

Figure 17. Comparison of fuel oil costs of the heating medium over the entire control period for control setups of tube MPC (circles), summarised in Table 5 and PID controller (dashed):
a) control scenario I, b) control scenario II.

4. Conclusion

The offset-free implicit tube MPC strategy was designed and implemented for the HHIDiS using a simulation-based case study. The closed-loop control performance was evaluated against the conventional PID controllers under four different fouling levels. Two control scenarios were considered: reference tracking and disturbance rejection. Eight robust MPC configurations were analysed using control performance indicators, including RMSE and maximum overshoot. The results revealed that robust MPC significantly outperformed PID control in terms of RMSE, particularly under more aggressive tunings. However, this improvement came at the cost of increased overshoot, which was mitigated through conservative tuning (notably setup A), leading to more stable but slower control responses.

In addition to control performance, the analysis included environmental and economic metrics. The conservatively tuned MPC (setup A) achieved lower fuel oil consumption and reduced carbon footprint at lower fouling levels during condenser step changes. Under higher fouling conditions, aggressively tuned MPCs performed comparably or slightly better than PID. In the reboiler step change scenario, the conservative MPC outperformed the PID, while the aggressive MPC (setup H) yielded similar results to those of PID control.

This study demonstrated that robust MPC improved both temperature and pressure control in HHIDiS systems under operational uncertainty, reducing RMSE by up to 35% and significantly decreasing or eliminating overshoot. The effects of varying fouling levels were observed - while performance degraded with increased fouling in all cases, robust MPC maintained better control accuracy and stability than PID. Notably, conservative tuning ensured zero overshoot across all levels of fouling, while aggressive tuning improved speed at the cost of increased oscillations. Additionally, the proposed strategy contributed to reduced energy usage and CO₂ emissions, offering tangible economic benefits over conventional PID control. These results underscore the adaptability of robust MPC tuning in prioritising either control precision or stability, depending on operational goals.

While the current case study is limited to simulation-based numerical analysis, it lays a solid foundation for future analysis that includes experimental validation and extension to challenging multicomponent mixtures. The proposed optimisation-based robust MPC framework presents a viable and scalable alternative to traditional PID control for energy-efficient, environmentally conscious industrial distillation systems.

Nomenclature

Symbols

0: zero matrix

A: heat transfer surface of HME, m²

A: system matrix of the state space model

$\tilde{\mathbf{A}}$: system matrix of the augmented state space model

B: molar heat of vaporisation (condensation), kJ/kmol

B: input matrix of the state space model

$\tilde{\mathbf{B}}$: input matrix of the augmented state space model

c: mass or molar specific heat, kJ/(kg·K) or kJ/(kmol·K)

C: output matrix of the state space model

$\tilde{\mathbf{C}}$: output matrix of the augmented state space model

d_{C1}, d_{C2} : internal and external tube diameter of condenser, m

d_{R1}, d_{R2} : internal and external tube diameter of reboiler, m

dA : differential of the area of HME, m²

$d\dot{Q}$: differential of the heat duty of HME, W

dt : differential of time, s

e_{CO_2} : CO₂ emissions from fuel oil combustion, kg/kJ
E: disturbance matrix
f: implicit tube projection into the state and input constraints
g: gravitational acceleration, m/s²
G(s): operator transmittance
G_C: transfer function of a controller
 h_b : convective boiling heat transfer coefficient, W/(m²·K)
 h_c : condensation heat transfer coefficient, W/(m²·K)
 h_L : heat transfer coefficient for liquid, W/(m²·K)
 h^L, h^V : molar enthalpy of liquid and molar enthalpy of vapour, kJ/kmol
I: identity matrix
k: sample of discrete-time domain, s
 k_A : vapour-liquid equilibrium constant of component *A*
K: LQR gain
 K_D, K_I, K_P : derivative, integral and proportional gain
 l_C, l_R : length of the condenser and reboiler tubes, m
 m_{Ct} : mass flow rate of cooling water in condenser, kg/s
 m_{Rs} : mass flow rate of heating water in reboiler, kg/s
 \dot{m} : mass flow rate, kg/s
M: number of evaluated control steps
 M_{R2} : mass of liquid in the rectifying section R2 in column C2, kg
 M_{S1} : mass of liquid in the stripping section S1 in column C1, kg
v: manipulated variable
 n_C, n_R : total number of condenser and reboiler tubes
 n_w : total number of uncertain parameters
 n_i : total of integral action member
 n_u, n_x, n_y : total number of system inputs, states and outputs
N: prediction horizon
 N_i, N_j : number of moles in the cell on the rectifying and stripping side, mol
 \dot{N}^L, \dot{N}^V : molar flow rate of liquid and molar flow rate of vapour, kmol/h
 N_C : total number of system states and inputs constraints
 N_S : total number of control steps generating the tube
 N_W : total number of vertices of the uncertainty set
P: Lyapunov matrix
 p_j : pressure in the condenser and the stripping section, kPa
 p_i : pressure in the reboiler and the rectifying section, kPa
 Pr_L : Prandtl number for liquid
Q: penalty matrix of the augmented system states
 \dot{Q} : heat duty of HME, W
 \dot{Q}_C, \dot{Q}_R : heat duty of condenser and heat duty of reboiler, W
 $\mathbf{Q}_i, \mathbf{Q}_x$: penalty matrix of integral action member and penalty matrix of system states
r: reference value
 r : heat of vaporisation (condensation), kJ/kg
R: penalty matrix of system inputs
 \mathbb{R} : Euclidean space of real numbers
 R_f : thermal resistance of fouling, m²·K/W
 Re_L : Reynolds number for liquid
s: Laplace operator
t: time, s

T : temperature, °C
 ΔT : temperature difference, K
 T^L, T^V : temperature of liquid and temperature of vapour, °C
 T_{Rto} : temperature in reboiler, °C
 T_S : sampling time
 \mathbb{T} : invariant approximation of the minimal robust positively invariant set
 \mathbf{u} : inputs of the state space system, kg/s
 $\hat{\mathbf{u}}$: nominal part of the system inputs, kg/s
 \mathbb{U} : polytope of constraints on input variables
 U_f, U_{ij} : overall heat transfer coefficient in the fouled and clean HME, W/(m²·K)
 p : unit price of fuel oil, USD/kJ
 V : volume, m³
 V_m : wall volume for the cell i, j , m³
 \mathbf{w} : uncertain parameters
 \mathbb{W} : set of uncertain parameters
 \mathbf{x} : states of the state space system
 x_A, y_A : mole fraction of component A in the liquid and vapour phase
 \mathbf{x}_i : integral action member
 $\tilde{\mathbf{x}}$: augmented vector of state variables
 $\hat{\mathbf{x}}$: nominal part of system states
 $\hat{\mathbf{x}}_0$: initial condition of $\hat{\mathbf{x}}$
 \mathbb{X} : polytope of constraints on system states
 \mathbb{X}_F : feasibility set
 \mathbf{y} : outputs of state space system
 \mathbf{y}_0 : initial condition of output variable
 \mathbf{y}_∞ : steady-state value of output variable
 \mathbf{y}_{MAX} : maximal value of output variable

Superscripts

L, V : liquid and vapour

Subscripts

C, R : condenser and reboiler
 Cs, Rs : condenser and reboiler shell-side
 Csi, Cso : inlet and outlet to/from the condenser shell-side
 Ct, Rt : condenser and reboiler tube-side
 Cti, Cto : inlet and outlet to/from the condenser tube-side
 i, j : -th cell on the rectifying side and the stripping side
 m : wall
 Rsi, Rso : inlet and outlet to/from the reboiler shell-side
 Rti, Rto : inlet and outlet to/from the reboiler tube-side
 $R1, R2$: rectifying section R1 in column C1 and rectifying section R2 in column C2
 $R1i, R1o$: inlet and outlet to/from the rectifying section R1 in column C1
 $R2i, R2o$: inlet and outlet to/from the rectifying section R2 in column C2
 s : steady state value
 $S1, S2$: stripping section S1 in column C1 and stripping section S2 in column C2
 $S1i, S1o$: inlet and outlet to/from the stripping section S1 in column C1
 $S2i, S2o$: inlet and outlet to/from the stripping section S2 in column C2
 z : including thermal resistance of the fouling layer

Greek letters

α : auxiliary parameter of uncertainty tolerance
 α_{RT} : volume fraction of vapours in a two-phase mixture on the tube-side of the reboiler
 β : hold up of liquid, %
 η : furnace efficiency
 η_L : liquid viscosity, Ns/m²
 κ : control law
 λ_L : thermal conductivity of liquid, W/(m·K)
 π : number pi
 σ_{MAX} : maximum overshoot
 φ_L : ratio of two-phase to liquid-phase frictional pressure drop
 ρ : density, kg/m³
 τ : implicit form of T
 ω : sequence of uncertainties

Abbreviations

CV: controlled variable
DWC: dividing wall column
HIDiC: heat-integrated distillation column
HHIDiS: hybrid heat-integrated distillation system
HME: heat and mass exchanger
MILP: mixed-integer nonlinear programming
IAE: integral absolute error
LMI: linear matrix inequalities
LTI: linear time-invariant
LQR: linear-quadratic regulator
MPC: model predictive control
MV: manipulated variable
PID: proportional-integral-derivative
RDWC: reactive dividing wall column
RMSE: root mean square error
TEMA: tubular exchanger manufacturers association
ULTI: uncertain linear time-invariant
VRC: vapour recompression

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Erika Pavlovičová: Investigation, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing, Software, Methodology, Validation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Visualisation. **Juraj Oravec**: Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Project administration, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Conceptualisation. **Marian Trafczynski**: Methodology, Validation, Project administration, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing, Conceptualisation, Supervision, Data curation, Funding acquisition, Visualisation. **Mariusz Markowski**: Funding acquisition, Writing – review & editing, Methodology. **Slawomir Alabrudzinski**: Software, Data curation, Funding acquisition. **Piotr Kisielewski**: Software, Visualization. **Krzysztof Urbaniec**: Writing – review & editing.

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Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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